

An Investigation of the Rotor Position Influence on the Broadband Phase Impedance - Application to SFRA Diagnosis

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Abstract—Sweep Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA) applied to rotating machines diagnosis and monitoring lacks of widespread industrial applicability up to this date. Several authors identify the rotor position influence as one of the main obstacles for an on-site and cost-effective diagnosis. This work provides a thorough investigation on how the rotor affects the broadband phase impedance of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM). The study is developed in several stages including analytical, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and experimental measurements. The rotor field is identified as the main cause for this rotor position influence. In addition, the magnetic excitation of the stator coils and thus, the coil distribution, play a significant role on the broadband impedance variation.

Index Terms—fault diagnosis, frequency response analysis, high-frequency

I. INTRODUCTION

Sweep Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA) is a standardized technique currently utilized for power transformer on-site diagnosis. Some of the most common scenarios when SFRA is applied are the transformer installation or relocation, factory short-circuit testing, and protocol diagnostic measurements [1]. The working principle of this technique is founded on the broadband measurement (i.e., from few Hz to the MHz band) of the impedance or admittance of the specimen under test, which resembles a RLC circuit. The different measurements taken over the transformer lifetime are compared to a baseline reference, which represents the healthy state of the machine. The differences with respect the baseline reference point out different faults or malfunction indicators.

The application of SFRA in the context of rotating machines remains confined to research studies and lacks standardiza-

tion as of yet. The main difficulties are related to the lack of expertise on different faults and ageing impact, and on the method sensitivity to the machine geometry and rotor position [2]. Since the early 2000s several authors explored the application of SFRA to detect phase-to-phase and interturn in low-voltage stator winding faults [3]. This research trend continued throughout the years in works such as [4], [5], where SFRA is utilized to detect faults in low-voltage induction machines. Lamarre et al. [6] propose the SFRA to detect insulation ageing and to discuss the utility of winding reversal in hydro generators. The utility of this technique to detect winding ageing is extended in [7] and [8], where the variation of impedance curves is studied under different insulation ageing mechanisms (e.g., thermal, moisture presence, etc.). Another research trend consists of the application of SFRA to detect short-circuit failures in the field winding of synchronous machines [9], [10]. The on-line variant of SFRA offers the advantage of continuous monitoring of the winding electrical signature. Sant'Ana et al. [11] presents a directly connected coupling that allows the on-line connection of the measurement apparatus. In [12] the work is extended by utilizing an active cancellation technique. The main drawback of on-line SFRA is the noisiness of the results that may be derived from electromagnetic coupling or from the effect of the rotor position in the inductive frequency bands.

The rotor position effect represents one of the main uncertainties for both off-line and on-line SFRA application. Platero et al. [13] present the variation of the single phase admittance curves induced by the rotor position variation. The authors link the rotor position influence to the variation of airgap and state that SFRA must be performed at a reference rotor position to avoid false diagnosis. In [14], the authors demonstrate that machines with constant airgap (i.e., cylindrical rotor induction machine) are also influenced by the rotor position. The same phenomenon is observed in [15], where the phase impedance

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of an induction machine is measured with and without the rotor. A more recent work shows the three phases broadband impedance measurement for a low-voltage induction machine, where a clear difference in the inductive band between phases is observed [16]. The authors link the impedance difference between phases to the randomness of coil turn location (since they are randomly-wound). However, the rotor position influence assessment is not performed. All these research results point out that the rotor position induces a variation on the inductance over the different frequency bands. Different causes for this effect are discussed in [14], but no conclusion is provided. One of the most feasible causes is derived from the effect of the rotor field, which may be present as material remanence even if no magnets or field winding are present [17]. This is supported by Roger et al. [18], who demonstrates the variation of the inductance for iron cores under a constant large valued dc field over a broad frequency band. In addition, the field penetration in the iron core at high-frequencies is very low and it does not cross the airgap. This causes the inductance of the stator winding to dramatically decrease at increased frequencies.

The present work is aimed to clarify the effect of the rotor position on the stator broadband phase impedance. A 4.7 kW 8/12 concentrated winding Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) is utilized as a case study specimen. Section II presents the analytical study of the broadband impedance of a coil surrounded by a laminated iron core. Section III presents a magnetostatic Finite Element Analysis (FEA) aimed to determine the magnetic coil excitation for different rotor positions. Section IV presents the experimental measurement campaign for the machine under study. Section V discusses the main outcomes from the study and concludes the work.

II. ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS

The main aim of the present section is to analytically relate the stator winding broadband impedance to the dc flux imposed by the rotor magnets. The stator winding of a rotating electrical machine resembles a RLC circuit. Some examples of detailed broadband physical representations of windings are found in [19], [20]. The parasitic capacitance between stator winding and rotor is very small compared to the winding-to-ground or inter-turn capacitances and thus, the rotor mainly affects the series inductances and resistances. These are frequency dependent due to several phenomena linked to the skin and proximity effects in the conductors and the laminated iron core [21]. At certain frequency, eddy currents flowing within single laminations become significant, creating a reaction field that shields the main magnetic field within the slot. To analytically study the effect of the laminated iron core in the broadband series frequency dependent resistance and inductance, a single lamination geometry is considered as depicted in Figure 1 [20]. The one-dimensional solution for the y-component of the magnetic field strength along the z-axis is provided by [22]:

$$\overline{H_y(z)} = H_0 \frac{\cosh(kz)}{\sinh(kb)} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Single lamination geometry, magnetic field strength and current density distribution for high-frequency magnetic excitation [20]

where $\overline{H_y(z)}$ is the magnetic field amplitude in y direction along the z -axis, H_0 is the rms surface magnetic field value in the edges of the lamination when $z = b$, k is the complex term defined as $(1 - j)/\delta$, and δ is the penetration depth $\delta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi f \sigma \mu}}$. Thus, the magnetic flux flowing within a single lamination assuming perfect insulation between iron sheets is given by:

$$\overline{\Phi} = \int_{-b}^{+b} h \mu \overline{H_x(z)} dz = \frac{2\delta h \mu}{1+j} H_0 \tanh(1+j) \frac{b}{\delta} \quad (2)$$

where μ is the macroscopic low frequency magnetic permeability. Considering a coil with N turns wound around a core with an axial length d , $d/2b$ laminations, and assuming an infinitely small insulation thickness between iron sheets, the impedance of the coil can be expressed by the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \overline{Z} = \frac{\overline{U}}{\overline{I}} = \frac{j}{1+j} \frac{\delta d h \mu \omega}{\mathcal{L} b} N^2 \tanh(1+j) \frac{b}{\delta} \\ \overline{U} = j \omega N \overline{\Phi} \\ \overline{I} = \frac{H_0 \mathcal{L}}{N} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{L}$ represents the mean length of the magnetic field flux lines, ω is the pulsation, $\overline{U}$ is the induced voltage in the winding and $\overline{I}$ the current creating the main magnetic field. By separating the real and imaginary parts:

$$\begin{cases} L_{ac} = \omega \frac{h d \mu N^2}{\mathcal{L}} \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{\sinh(\xi) + \sin(\xi)}{\cosh(\xi) + \cos(\xi)} \\ R_{ac} = \omega^2 \frac{h d \mu N^2}{\mathcal{L}} \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{\sinh(\xi) - \sin(\xi)}{\cosh(\xi) + \cos(\xi)} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\xi = 2b/\delta$, which relates the field penetration depth to the lamination thickness. By defining the constant $k = h d N^2 / \mathcal{L}$ it is possible to define the direct dependency of L_{ac} and R_{ac} on the relative permeability and the frequency. Figure 2 shows the normalized amplitude of L_{ac}/k and R_{ac}/k . The figure shows how the frequency dominates the value of both reactance and resistance (i.e., imaginary and real part of the impedance respectively). However, the relative permeability

Fig. 2. Normalized amplitude for L_{ac}/k and R_{ac}/k with $2b = 5$ mm, $\sigma_{iron} = 2.38$ MS/m

Fig. 3. Low frequency hysteresis characteristic quadrant including different rotor positions and small amplitude high-frequency minor loops

influences the value of both terms almost linearly. Thus, the effect of the iron core is not negligible even if the flux penetration is limited at high frequencies.

The macroscopic relative permeability (i.e., μ_r) value depends on the direct excitation of the iron magnetic domains and thus, on the magnetic flux density in the considered iron geometry. For PMSM small signal frequency sweep in standstill conditions (utilized in off-line SFRA), the rotor is at a fixed position imposing a dc field in the iron core of the stator coils. Thus, the value of the permeability for a single coil impedance will vary depending on the rotor position along the machine air gap. The more saturated the iron core is, the lower the macroscopic permeability and the lower the impedance of the single conductors within a coil. Figure 3 exemplifies the minor loops traced by the small signal injection for different rotor positions. The macroscopic relative permeability is considered isotropic without consideration of the flux excitation direction.

III. MAGNETOSTATIC FEA

The main objective of the section is to link the variation of the macroscopic relative permeability with the different rotor positions of the machine under study. Table I shows the main machine characteristics and Figure 4 depicts the machine cross-section and physical sample. The winding connection is made by connecting four coils in series with one branch for each phase.

TABLE I
CASE STUDY PMSM MACHINE CHARACTERISTICS

Number of poles	8
Number of slots	12
Rated power	4.7 kW
Base speed	6000 rpm
Magnet remanence	1.345 T
BH curve data	M330-50A
Turns/coil	28
Winding connection	Series star

Figure 5 shows a B-field or magnetic flux density contour plot of the stator including the coils forming the machine winding and their tags. The absolute value of the B-field ($|B| = \sqrt{B_x^2 + B_y^2}$) is sampled in three points located in the center of a tooth (i.e., SP-PhA, SP-PhB, SP-PhC) for each phase. The contour plot also highlights that the coils within each phase have the same field distribution at a fixed rotor position. Figure 6 depicts the absolute value of the B-field for the three coils over a range of 90 mechanical degrees, where a periodicity of 45 mechanical degree is observed. The phase-to-phase current flows through coils with different field

Fig. 4. 8/12 PMSM, 4.7 kW with concentrated winding. (a) Cross-section, (b) physical sample

Fig. 5. B-field contour plot in the case study machine stator for rotor position $\theta' = 0$, d-axis aligned with phase A magnetic axis

Fig. 6. B-field absolute value samples in points SP-PhA, SP-PhB, SP-PhC with respect to the rotor position

distributions. Taking into account the winding connection and current path described in Figure 7 (a), it is possible to define the average B-field from a phase-to-phase perspective, which is computed following:

$$|B_{avg}| = \frac{B_{ph,in} + B_{ph,out}}{2} \quad (5)$$

where $B_{ph,in}$ and $B_{ph,out}$ represent the absolute value of the sampled B-field in the coils of the input and output phase respectively. Figure 7 (b) shows the result of equation (6) for different phase combinations over 90 mechanical degree.

The relative permeability and thus, the series inductance, resistance and the overall impedance are affected by the field distribution in the different coils. The initial BH magnetization curve (i.e., M330-50A BH characteristic at 50 Hz) provides information regarding these dependences. Note that only the trend can be accurately determined since this curve is obtained for one magnetic direction and it does not represent the real hysteresis characteristic of the material. The relative permeability is higher for lower values of B-field (i.e., the relative permeability is defined from the BH curve slope in different regions). Figure 8 shows the initial magnetization BH curve and the locations of the low-frequency operating points for different rotor positions. From the figure it is evident

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. (a) Winding connection schematic with current path for different phase connections, (b) Average B-field absolute value for different phase connections with respect the rotor position

Fig. 8. M330-50A initial magnetization BH curve at 50 Hz and operating points for the PhA-PhB estimated average B-field for different rotor positions

that the higher the B-field in the coils, the lower the low-frequency relative permeability of the material and the lower the impedance experienced by the phase-to-phase current.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The present section describes the experimental set-up and the results of the investigation at hand. The broadband impedance measurement is performed by utilizing an auto-balancing bridge impedance analyser (Agilent 4294A) in the frequency spectrum ranging from 100 Hz to 10 MHz. The test is performed by changing the rotor position while measuring the impedance between different phase combinations. The rotor has 8 poles, which indicates that the d-axis of the rotor will be aligned with a single coil axis every 45 degree. However, the rotor position range is extended up to 90 degree for data redundancy and reliability. The rotor position is swept in intervals of 15 degree and thus, seven different samples

Fig. 9. Different rotor positions for impedance measurement, (a) $\theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\theta = 45^\circ$, (c) $\theta = 90^\circ$

are taken for each phase combination. Figure 9 shows the machine under test with three different rotor positions while measuring impedance. The rotor position cannot be accurately defined in some cases because of the increased cogging torque when two phases are connected and some impedance offset is expected for some rotor positions that should provide coincident impedance values. The phases are now tagged as A'-B'-C' and they are not necessary coincident with the phases from Figure 5. Three measurement connections are implemented in order to obtain the phase-to-phase impedance between the three different phase combinations.

Figure 10 shows the measurement results obtained for the different phase combinations and rotor positions. The behaviour of the curves is mainly inductive up to a resonance point located around 600 kHz. From that point on, the impedance curve behaves in a more capacitive manner. The focus is placed in the inductive part of the impedance since it is mainly influenced by the series resistance and inductance. An evident amplitude offset is observed between different rotor positions for all phase combinations. The offset between different rotor positions defines two clusters of curves, one of them around a higher impedance value and a second one located at lower amplitude values. The details in Figure 10 show the curves corresponding to each rotor position in the different amplitude and phase clusters. Regarding phase variations, very little disagreement is observed over the inductive part of the curve. The main differences in the phase curve are located around the resonant point (i.e., in the band 100 kHz - 1 MHz). The phase traces follow two different trends in this band and they are grouped following the trend observed in the amplitude curves. The two amplitude clusters comprise different rotor position traces depending on the phase combination. It is observed that the traces in the higher amplitude cluster are always separated by a space of 45 mechanical degree. In this way, traces corresponding to 0° , 45° and 90° ; 15° and 60° ; and 30° and 75° are grouped in the higher amplitude cluster for the measurement between phases A'B', A'C', and B'C' respectively.

Table II displays numerical results about the impedance difference induced by the different rotor positions for different frequencies. The columns representing Avg. HI and Avg. LI re-

Fig. 10. Measured broadband phase impedance for different rotor positions and phase combinations with details, (a) Phases A'B', (b) Phases A'C', (c) Phases B'C'

fer to the average value of the impedance traces corresponding to the higher and lower impedance clusters respectively. The

relative difference between impedance clusters is computed following:

$$\frac{|Avg.HI - Avg.LI|}{(Avg.HI + Avg.LI)/2} \quad (6)$$

These numerical results point out that the impedance at a very low frequency is equal for all the rotor positions and phase combinations (i.e., at 100 Hz). The difference between clusters is almost identical over a wide frequency band (i.e., 600 Hz - 110 kHz), while the values start to converge towards identical values around the resonant point (i.e., around 600 kHz).

TABLE II
MEASURED IMPEDANCE CLUSTER VALUES OVER INDUCTIVE FREQUENCY BAND

Phase combination A'B'			
Frequency [Hz]	Avg. HI [Ω]	Avg. LI [Ω]	Relative difference
100	1.82	1.77	0.012
600	13.69	10.43	0.134
3500	75.25	57.22	0.136
20000	355.13	265.63	0.144
110000	1281.82	1000.72	0.123
620000	5052.39	4477.03	0.060
Phase combination A'C'			
100	1.80	1.74	0.018
600	13.71	10.65	0.125
3500	75.36	58.46	0.126
20000	355.12	273.12	0.130
110000	1291.48	1033.25	0.111
620000	4444.81	4366.049	0.008
Phase combination B'C'			
100	1.82	1.77	0.014
600	13.73	10.48	0.134
3500	75.30	57.46	0.134
20000	354.32	267.13	0.140
110000	1277.86	1004.69	0.119
620000	4961.10	4483.83	0.050

The 45 degree separation in the high impedance clusters coincides with the low average B-field repeatability over the considered 90 mechanical degree. Table III shows the comparison between the impedance amplitude measurement at 10 kHz and the phase-to-phase average B-field obtained in the FEA simulation. From these results it is evident that the high impedance results are associated with lower average B-field and viceversa. Note that the tagging of the phases between simulation and physical samples does not necessarily coincide.

The links between analytical exploration, FEA analysis and real machine measurement explain the physical phenomenon relating rotor field and broadband phase impedance variation over its inductive band. In addition, the influence of the winding connection and design is identified as a factor influencing the broadband impedance variation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a thorough investigation of the rotor position effect on the broadband stator phase impedance for a PMSM. This relationship is of importance for the SFRA reliability in rotating electrical machines. Firstly, an analytical exploration of the variables affecting the impedance of a coil with laminated core was performed. This exploration

TABLE III
EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATION VALUES FOR IMPEDANCE AMPLITUDE AND AVERAGE PHASE-TO-PHASE B-FIELD FOR DIFFERENT ROTOR POSITIONS

Experimental Measurement at 10 kHz			
Rotor position [deg.]	PhA'B'	PhA'C'	PhB'C'
	Z [Ω]	Z [Ω]	Z [Ω]
0	208.58	159.26	157.08
15	155.03	207.54	157.75
30	153.83	161.12	207.4
45	207.56	156.83	155.84
60	153.94	208.61	157.91
75	157.5	160.93	207.89
90	207.86	157.91	150.97
FEA magnetostatic simulation			
Rotor position [deg.]	PhAB	PhAC	PhBC
	avg. B [T]	avg. B [T]	avg. B [T]
0	1.217	1.216	0.842
15	1.129	0.834	1.216
30	0.838	1.215	1.214
45	1.217	1.216	0.842
60	1.219	0.844	1.216
75	0.838	1.215	1.214
90	1.217	1.216	0.842

highlighted the increase of the real and imaginary part of the impedance with the macroscopic relative permeability. Secondly, a magnetostatic FEA was performed for the machine under study, where the link between relative permeability, coil magnetic excitation and coil connection was presented. Finally, the broadband phase impedance measurement for different rotor positions over 90 mechanical degree was described and analysed. The comparison between the different results links the variation of the impedance inductive band with the rotor position, and defines the coil connection and design as an influencing factor. The main conclusion of the work lays on the fact that the rotor field represents one of the main causes for the lack of repeatability on the SFRA results including inductive impedance dominance. This could also be observed as material residual flux in cylindrical rotor machines with absence of rotor field in standstill conditions. The magnetic excitation (i.e., non-zero B-field in the iron core) with an operating machine during on-line measurement could represent one of the main noise sources. The measurement of broadband phase impedance for machines with distributed winding and cylindrical rotor represents an immediate step to extend this investigation. In addition, further work is necessary to discard or evaluate the hypothesis previously presented in [14]. This may eliminate some of the obstacles for SFRA standardization in rotating electrical machines such as the limited sensitivity against some failure and ageing mechanisms.

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